

A Systematic Review of Nosocomial Infection Prevalence in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

Hospital-acquired infection (HAIs) refers to infections contracted by patients during their hospital stay but not initially diagnosed. HAIs complicate units, including Critical Care, increasing illness, death, expenses, and hospital stays, typically 48-72 hours post-admission. The study aims at assessing the prevalence of Nosocomial infections West Bengal. Articles from 2013-2023 were identified via Google Scholar Advanced Search. 60 articles were analysed after undergoing screening based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. 06 articles were screened for analysis, considering gender, hospital stay duration, geographical diversity, and infection types. The study reveals the HAIs are notably more prevalent in Paschim Bardhaman and Nadia districts. Common causative agents include *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *E. coli*. The three main types of HAIs are RTIs, SSIs, and UTIs. Bankura patients face a particularly high risk of SSIs. The highest frequency of UTIs is seen in Nadia and Darjeeling.

Keywords: Hospital Acquired Infections, Surgical Wound Infection, Urinary Tract Infections, Device-associated infection and Intensive therapeutic unit.

INTRODUCTION

The terms nosocomial infections (NIs), hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), and healthcare-associated infections (HCAIs) refer to a variety of prevalent, serious public health issues that place a significant burden on healthcare systems in both highly industrialized and underdeveloped nations. These serious safety issues are related to the high mortality and morbidity and affect patients as well as healthcare professionals. Infection prevention is something hospitals should work to do in order to lower costs, length of stay, morbidity, and mortality.^{1,2,3,4} 8.03% of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) were reported in an Indian study. The safety and quality of healthcare depend on the monitoring of HAIs. Better cleanliness measures may be able to prevent 15–30% of HAIs, according to previous study. Campaigns to promote hand cleanliness have been successful in lowering HCAIs,

which has prompted national initiatives in India. Hospital infections, also known as Nis or HAIs, are contracted 48–72 hours after admission to healthcare facilities. Even after discharge, they may still have an impact on workers and patients.¹

Nosocomial infection sites

Figure 1 Sites of the most common nosocomial infections: distribution according to the French National Prevalence Survey (1996).⁶

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Major common infection:

1. Urinary tract infection (UTI):

A major health concern is associated with urinary tract infections (UTIs), which are brought on by bacterial activity in the urine system. In 70–80% of instances, hospital-acquired UTIs are the result of overuse of catheters. UTIs are very prevalent in developing countries.⁷

2. Nosocomial pneumonia (NP):

The second most common infection in critical care units, nosocomial pneumonia (NP), is a lung infection that develops 48 hours after admission. It primarily affects high-risk patients using mechanical breathing and has a high death rate and healthcare cost. There is still a lack of understanding and treatment for NP.⁸

3. Surgical site infection (SSI):

Staphylococcus aureus and *Enterococcus* produce a significant portion of infections, and incisional and organ-space surgical site infections are common.

After surgery, infections may develop outside of the incision, resulting in pus, an abscess, or the need for additional testing.

- a. Redness, discomfort, swelling, heat, or pus at the site are indicators of skin and tissue infections that can result from shallow incisions.
- b. Surgical infections can manifest in locations other than the incision, like organs or spaces, and they can be identified using a variety of techniques.⁹

4. Nosocomial Bacteraemia:

Five percent of nosocomial infections, significant case fatality rates (>50% for several pathogens), and rising frequencies of *Candida spp.* and multiresistant *Staphylococcus*.¹⁰

5. Other nosocomial infections:

- a. Infections of the skin and soft tissues.

- b. The most frequent nosocomial illness in children is rotavirus, whereas, in industrialized countries, the most frequent nosocomial cause of adult gastroenteritis is *Clostridium difficile*.
- c. After childbirth, infections of the reproductive organs can arise, including endometritis.

Factors influencing the development of nosocomial infections:

- i. The microbial agent
- ii. Patient susceptibility
- iii. Environmental factors
- iv. Bacterial resistance¹²

Transmission and Prevention of Nosocomial Infection:¹³

1. Modes of Transmission:

a. The patient's endogenous infection (permanent or temporary):

Normal flora bacteria cause infection by spreading, damaging tissue, or overgrowing due to antibiotic use. Gram-negative gut bacteria cause surgical and urinary infections.

b. Exogenous cross-infection, or flora from a different patient or employee:

Bacteria spread through direct contact, airborne droplets, contaminated staff, objects, and environmental sources like water and food.

c. Flora from the health care environment (endemic or epidemic exogenous environmental infections):

Several types of bacteria thrive in the host environment:

- i. Pseudomonas, Acinetobacter, and Mycobacterium are sometimes found in sterile

goods or disinfectants, as well as in water and wet environments.

- ii. In goods used in care, like linen, equipment, and supplies, good housekeeping typically reduces the chance of germs surviving; because most microbes need heat, humidity, and nutrition to survive.
- iii. In food.
- iv. Since microorganisms smaller than 10 μm in diameter are present in both droplet nuclei and fine dust created by speaking or coughing, they can be consumed in a manner similar to that of fine dust.

2. Standard precautions control practice:

Treating all patients in healthcare facilities requires following essential precautions: hand hygiene, personal protective equipment, proper handling of equipment and soiled linen, needlestick prevention, environmental cleaning, and waste management.

3. Hand hygiene:

Hand hygiene is crucial in preventing hospital infections, but compliance is often inadequate. Reasons for this include limited access to equipment, high staff-to-patient ratios, allergies to handwashing products, inadequate staff knowledge, lengthy recommended washing duration, and time constraints.

4. Cleaning and disinfection of the environment:

- A. Clean hospital environment, free from dust and soil.
- B. Routine cleaning removes visible dirt containing 90% of microorganisms through mechanical action; soap and detergents lack antimicrobial properties.
- C. Classify areas into four hospital zones for appropriate asepsis methods:
 - i. **Zone A:** Non-patient admin, library tasks – no patient contact.

- ii. **Zone B:** Clean non-infected patients with a dust-free method, and avoid dry sweeping/vacuuming. Use a detergent solution. Disinfect contaminated areas before cleaning.
- iii. **Zone C:** Isolate patients, clean with disinfectant, and separate equipment for each room.
- iv. **Zone D:** Clean susceptible areas with separate equipment, and detergent/disinfectant.

5. Disinfection:

Prevent transmission; not complete sterilization; remove microorganisms.

- A. Act without regard to the quantity of bacteria present, the degree of water hardness, the presence of soap, or the presence of proteins (that inhibit some disinfectants).
- B. Manufacturers' recommendations dictate the disinfection level needed for various patient care activities (high, intermediate, low).
 - i. **High-level disinfection (critical):** Destroy microorganisms, except for heavily contaminated bacterial spores.
 - ii. **Intermediate disinfection (semi-critical):** Inactivates TB, bacteria, viruses, and fungi; may not kill spores.
 - iii. **Low-level disinfection (non-critical):** Broad-spectrum, limited effectiveness against resistant bacteria and spores.

6. Personal protective equipment:

PPE is a range of protective barriers like gowns, masks, gloves, and eyewear that shield against infectious agents. It reduces transmission and protects both healthcare workers and patients from exposure to infections.

7. **Vaccination:** Vaccinating healthcare workers protects them from infections and prevents

transmission to patients, ensuring the safety of both parties.

Table 1 Vaccines Used in hospital-acquired infections (HAIs)

Vaccine	Dose and Remarks
Hepatitis B	Three-dose series at 0 as well as 1 and 6 months
Measles, Mumps and Rubella (MMR)	Two doses four weeks apart
Influenza	Follow India's vaccine recommendations for protection against current strain
Tetanus	Booster once every 10 years
Varicella	HCW without immunity: 2 varicella vaccine doses, 4 weeks apart.

METHODOLOGY

The database search was done using search engine-Google Scholar advanced search. The keywords included for search Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), healthcare-associated infections (HCAIs), and nosocomial infections (NIs) in West Bengal.

Articles published in between 2013 to 2023 were selected. 254 articles were included for analysis which were further screened using inclusion and exclusion criteria. 6 articles were finally screened for analysis based on gender, duration of stay in the hospital, geographical diversity, and types of infection. The review of the process was done by two independent reviewers KHR and KAA.

Figure 2 Methodology for systematic review

Article Search

A comprehensive search was conducted using Google Advanced Search to gather information on hospital-acquired infections in the West Bengal region of East

India. The search query included variations such as "Hospital Acquired Infections," "Hospital Associated Infections," "Healthcare-Associated Infections," and "Nosocomial Infections." A total of 270 articles were found, providing a significant dataset for analysis and

understanding of the prevalence and management of these infections in the healthcare settings of West Bengal.

Table 2 Keywords for article search

Database	Search Query	Articles Found
Google Advanced Search	("Hospital Acquired Infections" OR "Hospital Associated Infections" OR "Healthcare-Associated Infections" OR "Nosocomial Infections") AND ("West Bengal" OR "East India")	270

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria for the study encompassed research published between 2013 and 2023, involving patients over 18 years who were hospitalized for more than 48 hours in West Bengal. Furthermore, the selected studies were required to align with the same

research theme, be accessible in published or pre-print formats, and offer insights addressing the research questions. Exclusion criteria excluded studies published in non-English languages, duplicates (totaling 16), and those presented in conference proceedings, book chapters, review papers, or lacking full-text availability.

Table 3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria to filter articles.

INCLUSION CRITERIA	EXCLUSION CRITERIA
The study should be published between 2013 and 2023	A study published in non-English languages
Patients should be above 18 years of age and should have stayed in the hospital for more than 48 hours	Duplicate articles = 16
Studies should be conducted in the state of West Bengal	Study with a conference, book chapter, review paper, and full-text non-availability
The study should have the same research theme	
The study should be available in a published or pre-print format	
The study should give answers to the research questions	

The most important inclusion criterion among all the inclusion and exclusion criteria in Table 3 is that the study must provide an answer to the research question. Therefore, in order to meet these requirements, the following three sub-criteria are defined:

- a. **Abstract-based Assessment:** After applying further inclusion and exclusion criteria, the abstract reading of the remaining articles is included in the abstract-based assessment. If the study is connected to the research theme, it is indicated by the abstract reading. The following set of evaluation criteria is applied to the papers whose abstracts most closely match the study theme.
- b. **Full text-based Assessment:** This requires reading the article as its whole. Studies that are in line with the research theme are taken into consideration, while those that are not are rejected for additional examination. Following the full-text evaluation, the exams are assessed using the quality assessment.
- c. **Quality-based Assessment:** The literature review is better because of the quality-based assessment. The quality assessment criteria

outlined below are used for the research that meets the requirements for the full-text assessment.

Quality Assessment Criteria

The quality of research studies is evaluated using the following standards. A research study is not accepted for further review if it does not satisfy at least one of these requirements.

S1: Is the study discussing different infections or diseases that have occurred after hospital admission or before that?

S2: Is the study discussing different airborne diseases or contamination through hospital equipment or other different kinds of stuff?

S3: Is the study discussing different probable modes of transmission?

S4: Is the study discussing the diversity of HAIs in both genders?

S5: Is the study discussing the prevalence of different HAIs?

S6: Is the study discussing the distribution of different pathogens causing HAIs?

Systematic Review Steps

Steps involved in the process of systematic review are shown in Figure 3 like defining the research topic, searching on databases, filtering articles based on specific criteria, and finally, critically evaluating the

remaining studies. Figure 2 illustrates this process and shows how the number of articles gets refined at each stage.

Figure 3 Steps of systematic review

RESULTS:

a) Duration of hospital stay:

Studies were conducted in five districts of West Bengal i.e. Bankura, Nadia, Darjeeling, Paschim Bardhaman, and Kolkata. The minimum duration of staying in the hospital was 48 hrs. The number of patients who participated was 2062 in Bankura, followed by 578 in Kolkata, 346 in Paschim Bardhaman, 107 in Darjeeling, and 84 in Nadia (Table 04).

The highest no. of patients participated was 2062 in the district of Bankura and the lowest was 84 in the district of Nadia.

Table 4 Variation according to the time of hospital stay

Author (Year of Publication)	District	Total no. of subjects	Duration of stay
Dey R et al. (2019) ³	Bankura	2062	48 h
Nayek S et al. (2019) ⁵	Nadia	84	More than 48 h
De M et al. (2018) ¹⁴	Darjeeling	107	Less than 72 h
Thakur L et al. (2019) ²	Paschim Bardhaman	111	48 h
Singh P et al. (2022) ¹⁵		235	48h
Jana A et al. (2015) ⁴	Kolkata	578	More than 48 h

b) Diversity based on gender:

Gender diversity is tabulated in Table 05, which shows the ratio of males to females in the districts of Bankura is 1.15:1, 1.58:1 in Paschim Bardhaman, 2.21:1 in Kolkata, 0.9:1 in Nadia and 0.84:1 in Darjeeling. The Average no. of male and female patients is 334 and 258.4 respectively. The overall

number of male patients is higher than that of female patients, and the ratio of male patients is higher in the districts of Bankura, Paschim Bardhaman, and Kolkata, and the ratio of female patients is higher in the districts of Nadia and Darjeeling as indicated in Fig 04.

Table 5: Diversity based on gender

Author (Year of Publication)	District	Total no. of subject	Male	Female	Gender ratio
Dey R et al. (2019) ³	Bankura	2062	1104	958	1.15:1
Nayek S et al. (2019) ⁵	Nadia	84	51	53	0.9:1
De M et al. (2018) ¹⁴	Darjeeling	107	49	58	0.84:1
Thakur L et al. (2019) ²	Paschim Bardhaman	111	68	43	1.58:1
Jana A et al. (2015) ⁴	Kolkata	578	398	180	2.21:1
	Avg.		334	258.4	

Figure 4: Average diversity based on gender

c) Prevalence of HAIs:

According to a WHO report hospital-acquired infection rates in developing countries vary from 5.7% to 19.1% (but mostly >10%).¹⁴ The occurrence of HAIs (Table 06) in patients was 4.5% (92/2062) in the district of Bankura, 33.3% (28/84) in Nadia, 19.6% (21/107) in Darjeeling, 34% (80/235) in Paschim Bardhaman, and 19.6% (113/578) in Kolkata.

Table 6 Distribution of study subjects according to the growth of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs)

District	Total no. of subject	With HAIs (% prevalence)	Without HAIs (% prevalence)
Bankura	2062	92 (4.5%)	1970 (95.5%)
Nadia	84	28 (33.3%)	56 (66.7%)
Darjeeling	107	21 (19.6%)	86 (80.4)
Paschim Bardhaman	235	80 (34%)	155 (66%)
Kolkata	578	113 (19.6%)	465 (80.4%)

Figure 5 Diversity based on positive and negative cases of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs)

d) Prevalence of the most typical kind of HAIs:

HAIs can be hospital-acquired UTIs, SSIs, hospital-acquired pneumonia, bloodstream infections, etc. but the most commonly reported HAIs in all the districts were urinary tract infections (UTIs), surgical site infections (SSIs), and RTIs. Table 07 shows different no. of HAIs that are reported in the districts. UTIs

were reported 8 in Bankura, 15 in Nadia, 5 in Darjeeling, 21 in Paschim Bardhaman, and 36 in Kolkata. SSIs were reported 77 in Bankura, 6 in Nadia, 12 in Darjeeling, and 36 in Paschim Bardhaman but no SSIs were reported in Kolkata. RTIs reported in Bankura were 2, 9 in Nadia, 23 in Paschim Bardhaman, 49 in Kolkata, and no RTIs reported in Darjeeling.

Table 7 Distribution of different types of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs)

District	Urinary tract infection (UTI) (% prevalence)	Surgical site infection (SSI) (% prevalence)	Respiratory tract infection (RTI) (% prevalence)
Bankura	8 (8.7%)	77 (83.7%)	2 (2.2%)
Nadia	15 (53.57%)	6 (21.42%)	9 (32.14%)
Darjeeling	5 (23.81%)	12 (57.2%)	0 (0%)
Paschim Bardhaman	21 (22.1%)	36 (37.9%)	23 (24.2%)
Kolkata	36 (31.9%)	0	49 (43.4%)

Figure 6 Diversity based on the types of hospital-acquired infections (HAI)

e) Distribution HAIs causing pathogens:

HAIs may be due to different microorganisms like *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*,

Staphylococcus aureus, *Klebsiella* species, *Acinetobacter* species, *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida* species, *Enterococcus* species, *Citrobacter* species, etc. In Bankura, Darjeeling, Paschim Bardhaman, and Kolkata most common microorganisms that cause HAIs are *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* (Table 08). *E. coli* causing HAI cases are 19.57% in Bankura,

19% in Darjeeling, 32.49% in Paschim Bardhaman, and 15% in Kolkata. HAIs due to *P. aeruginosa* are 17.39% in Bankura, 23.8% in Darjeeling, 11.26% in Paschim Bardhaman, and 19.45% in Kolkata. *S. aureus* causing HAIs are 17.39% in Bankura, 19% in Darjeeling, 7.7% in Paschim Bardhaman, and 17.7% in Kolkata.

Table 8 Distribution based on nosocomial Infection causing micro-organisms

District	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Bankura	19.57%	17.39%	28.26%
Darjeeling	19%	23.8%	19%
Paschim Bardhaman	38.66%	5.67%	9.01%
Kolkata	26.31%	16.84%	6.32%
Kolkata	15%	19.45%	17.7%

Figure 7 Distribution based on nosocomial Infection causing micro-organisms

DISCUSSION

From the studies it was found that the highest no. of patients participated was 2062 in the district of Bankura and the lowest was 84 in the district of Nadia (Table 4). The overall number of male patients is higher than female patients. The ratio of male patients is higher in the districts of Bankura, Paschim Bardhaman, and Kolkata, and the ratio of female patients is higher in the districts of Nadia and Darjeeling as indicated in Fig 4. The highest prevalence of HAIs 34% is observed in the district of Paschim Bardhaman where a total of 235 patients participated out of which 80 patients suffered HAIs. In Nadia, the prevalence of HAIs is 33.3% which is quite close to that of Paschim Bardhaman. In the districts of Darjeeling and Kolkata, the Prevalence is

the same at 19.6%. The lowest prevalence is observed in the Bankura district which is 4.5%, here 92 patients suffered HAIs out of 2062 participated patients. The bar diagram (Fig. 05) shows the distribution of positive and negative HAI cases in different districts.

The most common types of HAI occurred in all the districts are represented in the bar diagram (Fig 06). Hospital-acquired UTIs are the highest at 53.57% in the district of Nadia, Hospital acquired SSIs are the highest at 83.7% in the district of Bankura, Hospital-acquired RTIs are the highest at 43.4% in the district of Kolkata when compared with all the districts. The distribution of different pathogens causing HAIs is plotted in the bar diagram (Fig 07). *E. coli* caused the highest 32.48% HAIs in Paschim Bardhamana and the lowest 15% HAIs in Kolkata, *P. aeruginosa* caused

the highest 23.8% HAIs in Darjeeling and the lowest 11.25% HAIs in Paschim Bardhaman, *S. aureus* caused the highest 19 % HAIs in Darjeeling and lowest 7.7% HAIs in Paschim Bardhaman.

CONCLUSION:

It is possible to conclude from a search of multiple studies in the scientific literature that there is a significant worldwide impact of HAI in terms of morbidity, death, additional costs, emotional stress, and other outcome indicators. This study indicates that a significant risk to patient health may be posed by the numerous pathogenic bacteria that are continuously present in hospital environments. For this reason, it's critical to regularly check hospital ambient air for air-borne infections. HAI prevalence is very much higher in the districts of Nadia and Paschim Bardhaman. In India, the HAI rate is alarming and is estimated at 30-50% of all hospital infections according to the World Health Organisation.⁵ Common pathogens that cause HAIs are *Escherichia coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa*. The very common types of HAIs are UTIs, SSIs, and RTIs. In Bankura, patients are mostly prone to SSIs. In Nadia and Darjeeling, UTIs occur in the highest number. In Paschim Bardhaman and Kolkata, RTIs and UTIs are very common HAIs among patients. The probable reasons behind these HAIs may be low hygiene maintenance during hospital stays, improper infection prevention and control, use of properly uncleaned surgical devices, etc. along with overuse of antibiotics. The proper reasons behind these HAIs should be investigated. Proper guidelines should be prepared regarding controlling the HAIs and necessary precautions should be taken to lower HAIs.

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